

IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION

Dr. Suunil Losarwarr Director Sharadchandra Pawar Institute of Management, Otur, Tq. Junner,
Dist. Pune, sglosarwar69@gmail.com

Abstract:

'Covid19'- pandemic has been a watershed event for the world in every aspect. IT is playing a vital role during the lockdown by enabling business continuity. It has changed mind set towards digitization, which has demonstrable benefits for business continuity, ease of working, and collaboration capabilities. Education is also not an untouched sector, in fact it is the most highly impacted sector. Delay in entrance examination, admission, classes etc. are the subsets of this impact. This paper is an attempt to address these issues. The paper foresees an attempt to identify the factors affecting student learning through online mode and further check the impact of these factors on students satisfaction level. The result focus upon the acceptance of students in this totally changed environment and problems encountered. Given the changing dynamic environment, the present study which is descriptive in nature attempts to understand the need, problems, challenges faced by students in adopting this new mode of learning focusing upon students undergoing higher education. Purposive sampling was used to arrive at a sample size of 300.

Keywords: Higher education, technology, online mode, student satisfaction and learning.

Introduction

The Covid-19 crisis has resulted in a tectonic shift in our education system. Major universities and higher education institutions have partially or fully shifted to online mode of teaching and are reporting considerable success in their endeavours.

The role of technology in shaping the current Education and its future vistas is the buzzword today. In earlier few years attention was usually focused on how technology was changing the way we live and work, and how 'game changer' ideas such as smart phone revolution, artificial intelligence (AI), augmented reality (AR), robotics, block chain technologies and Internet of Things (IOT) would usher changes at a much faster pace than ever before, but this sounds like a dream come true the next day when seen. The situation has been transformed so dramatically, so quickly. Role of technology has become predominant and its impact will be felt much more comprehensively in the field of education.

Tech enabled learning can not only bring transformational change in online education experience, it can also enhance and supplement regular classroom based pedagogy. It could offer more flexibility and learning support than the traditional formats. Technology offers teachers the opportunity to become more collaborative and extended learning beyond classrooms. Educators could create learning communities comprising students, fellow educators and experts in various disciplines around the world.

Across the country, the government of India is encouraging several e-learning projects under the National Mission on Education through ICT initiatives such as Swayam, Swayam-Prabha, National Digital Library, e-Yantra, Virtual Lab that are helping students as well as teachers in upskilling as well as providing them quality resources. In addition, these efforts are leading to creation of knowledge tools which encourage creativity and innovation, particularly among young students.

The New Education Policy (NEP) 2020 was announced in last week of July 2020. It replaces the earlier policy introduced 34 years ago, and envisages major reforms in the education system. It

focusses a real deal on technology use and integration. NEP recognises that India is a global leader in information and communication tech and cutting edge domains, such as space. The Digital India campaign is helping to transform the entire nation into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. While education will play a critical role in this transformation, technology itself will play an important role in the improvement of education is bi-directional.

It is proposed to set up an autonomous body, the National Educational Technology Forum (NETF) to provide a platform for free exchange of ideas and use of technology to enhance learning, assessment, planning, administration and so on both for school and higher education. The government will also set up the National Research Foundation (NRF), to initiate and expand research efforts in technology. NRF will play an important role in advancing core AI research, developing and deploying application-based research and advancing international research efforts to address global challenges.

The covid-19 crisis has resulted in a tectonic shift in our education system. Major universities and higher education institutions have partially or fully shifted to online mode of teaching and are reporting considerable success in their endeavours. Further, availability of world-class tech platforms has enabled them to smoothly transition to online delivery mode.

Our understanding of Covid-19 continues to evolve. The need of social distancing will continue to affect traditional learning processes. A "new normal" in education might emerge which will possibly have a lasting influence on pedagogy and assessment. Online education also has challenges. Conducting remotely proctored exams is perhaps the most important challenge. Replacing exams by project or take-home challenges can provide some viable and cost effective alternatives. For conducting laboratory classes and hands on exercises for remote students, there may be a need to design and deploy a tool box of online, virtual and remote labs that can be used in different courses to bridge this gap. Another limitation is lack, or absence of, human touch. Blended learning, using a mix of online and on-campus sources could be an option.

In a multi-lingual country like ours, language barriers create complexities. Cutting edge research in text translation and machine learning aims to create deep-learning systems that can translate English lectures into a student's native language. Similar technologies in voice recognition and text summarisation can transcribe an entire lecture and reduce paragraphs of text into relevant bullet points. Capacity building of teachers will be crucial to the success of use of technology in education.

In a recent report by the World Economic Forum, that over a century ago, at the time of the Spanish Flu with when people were isolating themselves, many (mostly Americans) turned to telephone to get in touch with friends and family. The Spanish flu underscored how essential the technology of telecom was to modern society. Possibly we are at a similar inflection point in time today. Prime Minister Narendra Modi has given a clarion call for Atmanirbhar Bharat. It goes much beyond being a self-reliant nation; it envisages India's leading role in the global arena

As a leader in technology and global supply chain of goods and services At the same time, it is also a social change paradigm where every individual is encouraged to strive for excellence and realising national potential.

Literature Review

Basilaiia, G., & Kvavadze, D. (2020) in their paper Transition to Online Education in Schools during a SARS-CoV-2 Coronavirus (COVID-19) Pandemic in Georgia, highlighted in their paper that the capacities of the country and its population to continue the education process at the schools in the online form of distance learning, study reviews the different available platforms and indicates the ones that were used by the support of the government, such as online portal, TV School and Microsoft teams for public schools and the alternatives like Zoom, Slack and Google Meet, EduPage platform that can be used for online education and live communication and gives examples of their usage.

In a seminar on 16th June 2020, Synthesis Report, Dr. MahraMutaiwei suggested that in past, education systems around the world were used to a certain pattern in which change was only superficial. This pandemic situation of Covid has definitely pushed the education systems around the

world to move out of their comfort zone and find out creative and innovative strategies and solutions and adopt a new teaching and learning platform for students.

ElfakiNahid. et.al. (2019) in their paper indicated that E-learning has significantly improved the performance academically and even the learning process. The grades of students proved to be better and improvised as compared to traditional mode. They also stated that it has a positive impact on student's achievements. E-portfolio has resulted in improvement of attitude and student motivation and has a positive impact on student's attitude towards E-learning.

WahibAli(2020) in his research highlighted the need of face to face classes globally due to the spread of Covid-19. He also revealed the vulnerabilities in education systems across the world. He emphasized the change demanded by the environment through online mode of learning. The findings of the study revealed that universities and colleges across the globe have adopted online learning and E-learning. Apart from availability of resources, readiness of the staff, confidence, accessibility of internet with the students and motivation played a very important role in adapting this new tech environment of education. The study was exploratory in nature and proposed the use of technology and hi-tech gadgets by teaching staff will enhance learning in this exceptional times.

Objectives of the study

- To identify the factors for effective learning in online mode
- To study the impact of identified factors affecting the satisfaction level of students.

Hypotheses:

- H₀₁: There is no significant impact of effectiveness of Teaching resource on student level of satisfaction
- H₀₂: There is no significant impact of online skill development on student level of satisfaction
- H₀₃: There is no significant impact of continuous assessment on student level of satisfaction
- H₀₄: There is no significant impact of availability of resources with students on student level of satisfaction
- H₀₅: There is no significant impact of traditional/offline teaching on student level of satisfaction
- H₀₆: There is no significant impact of efficiency of software on student level of satisfaction

Research Method:

The current study is descriptive in nature. This study examines the factors responsible for effective learning in online mode. It explores the relationship between the identified factors and the satisfaction level of students. The results drawn from this study may assist in designing an effective strategy for the next phase of education that is online teaching and learning.

The Study

The study provides a good number of reasons as to why students are likely to learn effectively through online studies. According to the study, students have more control over their studies and have more opportunities at their disposal for reflection. It is reported that successful online students tend to be organized and are self-starters who can accomplish their work without close supervision (Picciano, 2017; Wang & Hu,2019). The study was an attempt to investigate the impact of online teaching on student learning.

The Sample

The sampling unit was constituted of the university students taking higher education. Total 300 responses were obtained through Purposive sampling. Quantitative Research design was used for the study.

The Tool for Data Collection

The study used formal methods like surveys for obtaining quantitative information with the help of structured questionnaire which were subjected to statistical tests of significance. Key variables from the review of literature were elaborately combined with the aim of developing an effective questionnaire to be used in this survey. Comrey and Lee's (1992) advise regarding sample size: 50 cases is very poor, 100 is poor, 200 is fair, 300 is good, 500 is very good, and 1000 or more is excellent. The data was collected from 300 students of private university taking higher education for various courses like Engineering, Management, Science, Journalism, Commerce and Humanities. The items used to measure the student's level of satisfaction and level of learning through online teaching and extracted scale items from the literature were modified according to the requirement.

The collected data further analysed using Factor analysis and regression.

Reliability of instrument

The concept of reliability suggests both stability and consistency of measurement. The reliability of the instrument was determined by the Cronbach's alpha which was found to be 0.927 the details are given in Table 1.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.927	37

Table 1

Results and Discussion

The break-up of the sample being: 44.9% respondents are females and 55.1% respondents are Male. The main purpose of this research phase was to examine the appropriateness of the items and the internal structure of the constructs that the instrument measures. For these reasons, the exploratory factor analysis was first conducted on the 37 items with a varimax rotation using SPSS. Exploratory factor analysis is a statistical method employed to increase the reliability of the scale by identifying inappropriate items that can be removed and the dimensionality of constructs by examining the existence of relationships between items and factors when the information of the dimensionality is limited (Netemeyer, Bearden, & Sharma, 2003).

In this study, the seven factors (i.e., Teaching Resource, Effectiveness of online learning, Online Skill development, Continuous Assessment, Availability of Resources for Online learning, Offline/Traditional Teaching learning and Efficiency of Software) were used to determine the impact of online teaching on student learning.

An initial analysis was run to obtain eigenvalues for each factor in the data. The Kaiser Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure verified the sampling adequacy for the analysis; KMO=.922 which is above Kaiser's recommended threshold of 0.6 or this measure varies between 0 and 1, and values closer to 1 are better. (Kaiser, 1974). The details of KMO and Bartlett's Test given in Table 2

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.922
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	6747.678
	df	666
	Sig.	0.000

Table 2

The Seven-factor structure in this study was composed of 37 items. Eleven items of factor 1 represent Teaching Resource, Six items of factor 2 represent Effectiveness of Online learning, Four items of factor 3 represent Online Skill development, Five items of factor 4 represent Continuous Assessment, Four item in the factor 5 represents Availability of Resources for Online learning, Four item in the factor 6 represents Offline/Traditional Teaching learning, and one item in the factor 7 represent Efficiency of Software. The details of the factors are provided below.

Table of factor Analysis
Factor 1: Teaching Resource

1	Skill and responsiveness of the instructor [Instructor was available and helpful]	0.887
2	Skill and responsiveness of the instructor [Instructor effectively used time during class periods]	0.87
3	Skill and responsiveness of the instructor [Instructor stimulated student interest]	0.868
4	Skill and responsiveness of the instructor [Grading was prompt and had useful feedback]	0.86
5	Skill and responsiveness of the instructor [Presentations were clear and organized]	0.853
6	Skill and responsiveness of the instructor [Presentations were clear and organized]	0.835
7	Course content [Course content was organized and well planned]	0.761
8	Course content [Course organized to allow all students to participate fully]	0.748
9	Course content [Course workload was appropriate]	0.711
10	Course content [Learning objectives were clear]	0.707
11	I like the idea of not having to drive/commute to the University / Institute.	0.037

Factor 2: Effectiveness of Online Learning

1	I feel that using this online mechanism for teaching and learning is more effective.	0.787
2	I dont mind if I never actually meet my instructor or classmates in person.	0.738
3	I believe that high-quality learning can take place even without face-to-face interaction.	0.725
4	I believe I can complete all my courses online without difficulty	0.642
5	I find online learning effective	0.628
6	I am comfortable with spending several hours of time on a computer/Phone.	0.583

Factor 3: Online Skill Development

1	Online teaching-learning has improved the following Skills [Soft skills]	0.787
2	Online teaching-learning has improved the following Skills [Employability Skills]	0.774
3	Online teaching-learning has improved the following Skills [Core skills]	0.765
4	Online teaching-learning has improved the following Skills [Critical thinking]	0.713

Factor 4: Continuous Assessment

1	I am able to manage my study time effectively and easily complete assignments on time	0.787
2	I am self-disciplined while attending classes (Attention and retention capacity)	0.665
3	I am motivated by the online content provided by my Professors.	0.599
4	I can collaborate with other students during online activities outside of class for group assignments.	0.565
5	I am willing to actively communicate with my classmates and Professors electronically	0.443

Factor 5: Availability of Resources for Online Learning

1	I am able to access the Internet from my computer/ Phone, without any difficulty.	0.764
2	Access to the Internet is easily available	0.713
3	I am comfortable with downloading and installing software on my computer / Phone	0.689
4	I feel comfortable composing text on a computer in an online learning environment	0.378

Factor 6: Offline/Traditional teaching learning

1	I would like to take a class where I get regular personal feedback from my instructors.	0.676
2	I am facing eyes irritation and health issues because of long hour seating for online learning.	0.626
3	I like new technologies that may require new approaches to learning and problem-solving	0.564
4	I possess sufficient computer keyboarding skills for doing online work	0.482

Factor 7: Efficient Software

1	Which Software/ Application you find easy to operate	0.893
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As a result of exploratory factor analysis (EFA), Seven-factor structure of the instrument of student readiness in online learning explained 64.48 percent of the variance in the pattern of relationships among the items.

Regression Analysis

The main purpose of this analysis is to understand the extent of the satisfaction level of students influenced by the six independent variables and suggest the measures that should be taken based on the results obtained by using SPSS 16.00 - Statistical Package for Social Sciences. The table below provides the data needed to perform the linear regression analysis. The model summary table suggested that the set of independent variables has moderate correlation (0.6) with dependent variable and is able to explain 40.7 percent of variation of the dependent variable.

Model Summaryb

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.638a	.407	.395	4.15280	2.058

a. Predictors: (Constant), Efficient Software , Teaching Resource , Offline/Traditional Teaching Learning, Availability of Resources for Online Learning, Continuous Assessment , Online Skill Development

b. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction level of students for Online Learning

The findings indicate relationship between student satisfaction and online learning. The R value 0.638 reveals high correlation. The R² value 0.407 indicates that Efficient Software, Teaching Resource, Offline/Traditional Teaching Learning, Availability of Resources for Online Learning, Continuous Assessment and Online Skill Development contributes about 39.5% of the variation in satisfaction process.

ANOVAa

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	3546.796	6	591.133	34.277	.000b
Residual	5173.719	300	17.246		
Total	8720.515	306			

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction level of students for Online Learning

b. Predictors: (Constant), Efficient Software , Teaching Resource , Offline/Traditional Teaching Learning, Availability of Resources for Online Learning, Continuous Assessment , Online Skill Development

In order to test the null hypothesis the paper turn to F test that requires an analysis of the variance identified in the ANOVA table above. There is a significant impact seen by Efficient Software, Teaching Resource, Offline/Traditional Teaching Learning, and Availability of Resources for Online Learning, Continuous Assessment and Online Skill Development on student satisfaction through online learning.

Coefficientsa

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-1.988	1.870		-1.063	.289
Teaching Resource	.029	.039	.043	.736	.462
Online Skill Development	.341	.087	.228	3.933	.000
Continuous Assessment	.604	.086	.394	7.051	.000
Availability of Resources For Online Learning	.373	.109	.179	3.422	.001
Offline/Traditional Teaching Learning	-.184	.105	-.085	-1.760	.080
Efficient Software	.122	.338	.016	.362	.718

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction level of students for Online Learning

Based on the nonstandard coefficients we obtain the regression equation:

$$y = -1.988 + 0.029 x_1 + 0.341 x_2 + 0.604 x_3 + 0.373 x_4 - 0.184 x_5 + 0.122 x_6$$

Satisfaction level of students for Online Learning(Y)= Efficient Software + Teaching Resource + Offline/Traditional Teaching Learning + Availability of Resources for Online Learning + Continuous Assessment + Online Skill Development

- H_{01} : There is no significant impact effectiveness of Teaching resource on student level of satisfaction
It can be seen that the p-value from the coefficient table is 0.462 which is greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis is not rejected, which means there is no significant relationship seen between effectiveness of teaching resource with student level of satisfaction.
- H_{02} : There is no significant impact of online skill development on student level of satisfaction
It can be seen that the p-value from the coefficient table is 0.000 which is less than 0.05. The null hypothesis can be rejected, which means there is significant relationship between online skill developments with student level of satisfaction.
- H_{03} : There is no significant impact of continuous assessment on student level of satisfaction
It can be seen that the p-value from the coefficient table is 0.000 which is less than 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected, which means there is significant relationship is seen between continuous assessments on student level of satisfaction.
- H_{04} : There is no significant impact of availability of resources with students on student level of satisfaction
It can be seen that the p-value from the coefficient table is 0.001 which is less than 0.05. The null hypothesis can be rejected, which means there is significant relationship between availability of resources with students on student level of satisfaction
- H_{05} : There is no significant impact of traditional/offline teaching on student level of satisfaction
It can be seen that the p-value from the coefficient table is 0.080 which is greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis is not rejected, which means there is no significant relationship seen between traditional/offline teachings on student level of satisfaction
- H_{06} : There is no significant impact of efficiency of software on student level of satisfaction
It can be seen that the p-value from the coefficient table is 0.718 which is greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis is not rejected, which means there is no significant relationship seen between efficiency of software on student level of satisfaction

Conclusion

The findings of the study reveals no significant impact of teaching resource, efficiency of software and traditional teaching Learning on student level of satisfaction whereas online skill development, availability of resources with students for learning and continuous assessment has significant impact on students satisfaction. Taking into consideration this devastating pandemic situation of Covid and measures adopted to avoid its spread across, like social distancing, lockdowns etc., which have triggered the educational institutions to choose the mode of online learning. The study has definitely revealed the fact that students are favouring this mode of learning, but expect a refined strategy to avoid the technical glitches. A systematic plan needs to be designed to involve fun-loving activities so as to make the mode of learning more effective and attention catching. However planning to conduct and educate the students out of the traditional physical classroom setup really requires a systematic thought process, coordination and effective decision making. a learning transformation can be enhanced by a climate of trust and support. Student's satisfaction on this point of time is essentially attention catching and necessary to prove the judiciousness of this mode of learning. This digital revolution can streamline the ambitions and anxiety of students regarding their career. In essence, COVID-19 has provided us with the opportunity to adopt online learning as education systems need to be abreast with the rapid emergence of new technologies, thus making online, blended and remote learning a necessity at tertiary level

It is further recommended to follow the below practices to enhance a better environment and culture of learning among the students:

Basic ICT enabled infrastructure to carry out this mechanism of learning in a smooth manner

Access to the teaching fraternity for various online platforms of learning.

Systematic training to utilize these platforms.

Limitation of the study

A larger sample size will help us to understand and provide a better view of reality towards online classes and online mode of learning. At this time of crisis where everyone is trying hard to win against the situation (Covid 19) it is vital to have a continuous education system which students will enjoy and at the same time it will enhance their knowledge.

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